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A novel aluminium alloy developed for additive manufacturing with superior properties at elevated temperatures

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Abstract - A novel aluminium alloy with superior thermal stability at elevated temperature is developed for metal additive manufacturing. Metal powder of this new AlSiFeMn alloy was produced with gas atomization. Crack-free and highly dense samples were successfully fabricated by the Powder Bed Fusion – Laser Beam method. The as-printed samples were of hardness ~200HV, tensile strength ~400MPa with fracture elongation ~1.0%. Annealing at 350°C, the hardness dropped to 140HV after 4 hours and kept stable AT 24hours. The tensile strength after 24h@350°C was ~400MPa with fracture elongation increased to 3.5%. The ability to maintain high hardness and strength after high temperature soaking render this novel alloy as highly thermal stable, and as a potential alloy for applications at elevated temperatures.

Keywords: Aluminium alloys; PBF-LB; Elevated temperature; Thermal stability

1. Introduction

Aluminium and its alloys are essential materials in structural applications due to their favourable strength-to-weight ratio and corrosion resistance. They are widely used in aerospace and automotive applications as well as areas where high thermal and/or electrical conductivities are needed. Additive manufacturing (AM) technique, especially the PBF-LB technology, can enable the fabrication of complex component with excellent properties. The rapid solidification in the PBF-LB process can also result in unique and refined microstructure [1]. The most popular and widely used aluminium alloy for PBF-LB is the AlSi10Mg alloy, due to its excellent printability and good properties. However, the strength of AlSi10Mg alloys dropped significantly after annealing at elevated temperatures, for example the stress-relieving heat treatment 2h@300°C [2]. There are many efforts to find new alloys with better thermal stability and mechanical properties at elevate temperatures [3]. The current work describes a novel alloy developed for that purpose [4].

2. Materials and Methods

The new AlSiFeMn alloy has Si, Fe and Mn as its main alloying elements, with Mg, Cr and some other elements as trace. Metal powder was produced with a gas atomizer at Elkem AS, Norway. The powder was then sieved to the size range 20-63µm.

A metal 3D printer, model SLM280 from Nikon SLM Solutions, were used to print cubic and tensile samples. The substrate plate was of AA7075 and kept at 200°C during the printing process. Argon was used as the protective gas. Different laser parameters like laser power (P, unit W), laser speed (V, unit mm/s) and hatching distance (HS, unit µm) were tried to find optimal process parameters.

The printed samples were examined by the means of light optical microscopy (LOM) and scanning electron microscope (SEM). Vickers hardness were measured with a load of 1Kg. Heat treatment was done in salt bath at 350 °C. Tensile tests were performed using a ZwickRoell testing machine.

3. Results and discussion

A SEM images of the gas-atomized powder is shown in Figure 1. The powder is of spherical shape with few satellites. The powder also showed very good flowability during printing trials. Cubic samples of size 10mm and miniature tensile bar samples were printed.

Figure 2 shows the cross-section microstructure of one as-printed samples. The as-built samples were crack-free, and of very few pores. The relative density based on image analysis is >99.5%.

Figure 1. Gas atomized AlSiFeMn powder for 3D printing.

Figure 2. LOM image of cross section along the build direction of one as-printed sample, with information of laser parameters.

The as-printed samples were of hardness ~200HV. The hardness change during annealing at 350 °C is given in Figure 3. The hardness dropped sharply with the first 4 hours to ~145HV. With longer holding time, the hardness changed little with a stable hardness ~140HV after 24 hours. One AlSi10Mg sample were also printed and tested. The as-printed hardness was 133HV. However, it dropped to 60HV after 24h@350°C heat treatment.

Figure 3. Evolution of hardness during annealing at 350°C of printed AISiFeMn samples.

The tensile test results for the as-printed and the 24h@350°C annealed samples were plotted in Figure 4. The as-printed samples reached 400MPa when fractured at only ~1% elongation. After annealing, it is interesting to notice that the ultimate tensile strength change little, still at 400MPa, with much improved elongation at 3-3.5%. When correlated to the hardness results, the as-printed sample is very brittle so that it experienced early fracture during tensile test. After annealing, the tensile strength actually dropped from the full potential of the as-printed state but gained a better elongation. The high strength, 400MPa, is seldom found for aluminium alloys after such a 24h@350°C heat treatment.

Figure 4. Tensile results of the as-printed and the 24h@350°C annealed AISiFeMn samples.

4. Conclusion

A novel AISiFeMn alloy was successfully developed with demonstrated superior thermal stability for the PBF-LB additive manufacturing process. Samples fabricated with this alloy can give hardness 140HV and a tensile strength of 400MPa, after 24hours annealing at 350°C. Further characterizations to reveal the mechanism behind such superior properties, and tensile testing at elevated temperatures, are on-going.

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